

Drone Based Transmission Line Inspection

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Abstract: The inspection of transmission lines is a critical task in power systems to ensure uninterrupted electricity supply and prevent faults. Traditional inspection methods are time-consuming, risky, and require manual effort. This project presents a drone-based transmission line inspection system that utilizes unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) for efficient monitoring of power lines. The proposed system integrates a drone equipped with a high-resolution camera, sensors, and wireless communication modules to capture real-time data of transmission lines. The drone can detect faults such as damaged conductors, insulator cracks, vegetation interference, and overheating components. The collected data is transmitted to a ground station for analysis. This approach improves safety by reducing human involvement in hazardous environments and enhances inspection accuracy. The system is cost-effective, time-efficient, and suitable for modern smart grid applications. The project demonstrates the potential of drone technology in revolutionizing power system maintenance and monitoring. The reliability of electrical power transmission systems largely depends on the timely detection and maintenance of faults in transmission lines. Traditional inspection methods are labor-intensive, time-consuming, and often expose personnel to hazardous environments. To overcome these limitations, this project focuses on the development and implementation of drone-based transmission line inspection system. The proposed system utilizes with high-resolution cameras and various sensors to capture real-time data and images of transmission line components such as conductors, insulators, and towers. The collected data are analyzed to identify defects like corrosion, cracks, vegetation encroachment, and loose fitting. The use of drones significantly improves inspection efficiency, accuracy, and safety while reducing operational costs and downtime.

Keywords: Drone, Transmission Line Inspection, UAV, Smart Grid, Fault Detection, Monitoring System.

I. INTRODUCTION

Overview

The reliability of electrical power transmission systems largely depends on the timely detection and maintenance of faults in transmission lines.

Traditional inspection methods are labor-intensive, time-consuming, and often expose personnel to hazardous environments. To overcome these limitations, this project focuses on the development and implementation of drone-based transmission line inspection system.

The proposed system utilizes with high-resolution cameras and various sensors to capture real-time data and images of transmission line components such as conductors, insulators, and towers.

The collected data are analyzed to identify defects like corrosion, cracks, vegetation encroachment, and loose fittings. The use of drones significantly improves inspection efficiency, accuracy, and safety while reducing operational costs and downtime.

This project demonstrates how drone technology, combined with image processing can revolutionize power line monitoring and maintenance, ensuring a

more reliable and sustainable power transmission network.

Transmission lines play a vital role in delivering electrical power from generating stations to consumers. Ensuring their reliability and safety requires regular inspection and maintenance to detect faults such as conductor damage, insulator failure, corrosion, and vegetation interference.

Traditionally, these inspections are carried out manually by ground crews or through helicopter surveillance, which are both time-consuming, costly, and risky due to the challenging terrain and high-voltage environment.

A simple and preliminary method that is only limited to detect tempered glass insulators was proposed by The method involves binarizing the image with a set threshold and then applying morphological operations, but this method does not address varying lighting conditions. Some other simple methods limited to detect glass insulators only are presented in . These methods suggested the use of color features for insulator detection. Other than the transmission line insulators, a recent study proposed a deformable part model (DPM) for detecting rod-insulators in high-speed railway catenary systems. The image acquisition system for this method is mounted on the top of the inspection vehicle, which takes close-shot images of the insulators from a fixed distance.

The image acquisition system is also equipped with light illuminators, which really help in pre-processing of the insulator images. Although this method shows good recall (above 98%), it suffers low precision (approximately three false positives per image). Li et al. proposed to use local and global saliency maps for separating the insulator region from a non-insulator region. Yu et al. presented an insulator segmentation method that evolves a curve iteratively using texture and shape priors. However, these methods only work when the texture and intensity of the background and the foreground regions are distinctive. This condition

normally occurs only when aerial images of insulators are taken from closer proximity.

Edge-based feature extractor was proposed in to detect porcelain insulators from images taken from unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV). However, did not present sufficient experimental results to support the robustness of their proposed methods against cluttered backgrounds.

In order to localize multiple insulators jointly, Zhao et al. proposed a Markov Random Field (MRF) model by grouping the appearance similarities of the glass and porcelain insulators. Although the proposed method is robust against the complex background, its effectiveness is guaranteed only when a group of insulators appear together in the image, which limits the application of this method.

In situations where sufficient training data is not available, these methods can provide a basic level of component detection. However, these methods are very prone to failure in case of slight variations in illumination and view point, which are inevitable in outdoor environments. With recent advancements in unmanned aerial vehicle technology, drone-based inspection systems have emerged as an efficient and safer alternative. Drones equipped with high-definition cameras, infrared sensors can capture detailed images and thermal data of transmission lines from various angles and altitudes. These data are then processed using image analysis or to identify potential faults automatically. The implementation of drone-based inspection not only enhances accuracy and safety but also significantly reduces inspection time and operational costs. Moreover, drones can access difficult or remote locations with ease, making them ideal for large-scale and high-voltage power line.

Project Background

The demand for electricity has been increasing rapidly due to industrial growth and population expansion. As a result, the power transmission network has also

expanded significantly. Maintaining such a large network requires regular inspection and monitoring. In conventional systems, faults such as broken conductors, damaged insulators, and vegetation interference are detected manually. These methods are inefficient and may lead to delayed fault detection, resulting in power outages and economic losses.

Drone technology offers a modern alternative by enabling automated inspection. A drone equipped with cameras and sensors can fly along transmission lines and capture real-time data. This data can be analyzed to detect faults and ensure proper maintenance.

The integration of drones with image processing and artificial intelligence further enhances the system by enabling automatic fault detection. This reduces human intervention and increases efficiency.

Thus, drone-based inspection systems are becoming an essential part of modern power system maintenance. Unlike earlier studies that use handcraft features, this study explores the robustness of the CNN features and uses them for the task of multi-type HV transmission line components detection in a highly cluttered environment.

Successful implementation of an embedded system for real-time processing of drone videos with CNN-based transmission line components detection framework. Unlike previous CNN-based transmission line component detection frameworks where the CNN-based detector is just focused to detect one type of insulator and GPU resources are left unused, this article successfully demonstrated the feasibility of using real-time transmission line component detector that is trained to detect nine different transmission line components with above 90% recall. Moreover, the CNN-based detector is optimized to fully utilize the GPU resources and exhibit real-time processing capabilities.

A light-weight and robust power line detection algorithm is also proposed in this paper.

A novel defect analysis method is proposed that can detect multiple defects in transmission line components, such as broken sheds in insulators, balisor fading, broken wires, rust in sag adjustors, splits in insulator, etc. Other than broken shed defects, these transmission line component defect analyzing methods have never been covered in previous studies.

A complete transmission line component inspection system is presented and its robustness and real-time performance are evaluated.

Proposed System

This section presents a detailed overview of the proposed system. Figure 1.2.1 gives a brief introduction to familiarize the reader with the visual properties (i.e., shape, color, etc.) of the transmission line components discussed in this paper. The actual functionality of these components is beyond the scope of this paper. As shown in Figure 1.2., the proposed system can detect nine different types of transmission line components, having different colors, sizes, and shapes. It is worth mentioning that the proposed system is scalable (can detect more types of electrical components) and requires minor modifications in training and detecting routines.

Figure 1

Example images of various types of transmission line components that can be detected by the proposed system. (a) Transmission tower; (b) lightning arrester (LA); (c) suspension-type—white porcelain insulator; (d) suspension type red porcelain insulator; (e) polymer

insulator; (f) spacer; (g) sag adjuster with bolted tension clamp; (h) vibration damper; and (i) balisor.

The overall system diagram of the proposed transmission line components inspection system is shown in Figure 1.2.2. Based on the implementation details, the inspection system is partitioned into two modules: (i) detection module and (ii) defect analysis module. The capturing and detection module is embedded on the Jetson TX2 board (does real-time processing), while the defect analysis module is implemented on the server machine.

Figure 2. Overall system diagram.

Figure 1.2.2 Overall system diagram.

In addition to the transmission line components detected by the proposed CNN-based detection framework, the electrical power line is detected using a novel algorithm, which is presented in FIGURE1.2.1. In contrast to the drone is flown 10~20 m away from the power line, which also prevents any possible damage to power line in case of sudden failure. In summary, the proposed system detects ten transmission line components and analyzes their defects. In the later sections, detailed explanations of those steps shown in Figure 1.2.2 are given.

Power Line Detection

Power line detection is a critical process in the inspection and monitoring of electrical transmission systems. It involves identifying the presence, position,

and condition of transmission lines using various technologies such as cameras, sensors, and image processing techniques. In drone-based inspection systems, power line detection plays a vital role in ensuring accurate fault identification and safe navigation of the drone.

Transmission lines are long, thin, and often difficult to detect due to their small diameter and complex backgrounds like trees, buildings, or sky. Therefore, advanced detection techniques are required to accurately identify these lines in real-time.

1. Importance of Power Line Detection

Power line detection is essential for several reasons:

Fault Identification: Helps in detecting broken conductors, damaged insulators, and sagging lines

Drone Navigation: Prevents collision of drones with power lines

Maintenance Planning: Enables early detection of faults, reducing downtime

Safety: Reduces risk for human workers by minimizing manual inspection

Efficiency: Speeds up inspection process compared to traditional methods

Accurate detection ensures reliable operation of the power system and reduces maintenance costs.

Microcontroller based for drone :

The Pixhawk Flight Controller is an advanced open-source autopilot system widely used in drones and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs). It acts as the central brain of the drone, controlling all flight operations such as stabilization, navigation, and communication.

Pixhawk is designed to support autonomous flight and is highly suitable for engineering applications like drone-based transmission line inspection. It can process real-time data from sensors and make decisions to control the drone without human intervention.

In a drone system, the transmitter works together with a receiver mounted on the drone. The user operates the transmitter using joysticks, and the commands are transmitted to the flight controller, which then controls the motors accordingly.

Flysky transmitters are well-regarded in the RC community for their reliability, advanced features, and user-friendly designs. Whether you are a beginner or a seasoned enthusiast, Flysky offers a range of transmitters to meet various needs in remote control applications. For more detailed specifications and purchasing options you can visit the official Flysky website or check online.

Figure 1.3 Block diagram of flight controller

FlySky FS-i6 Transmitter :

The FlySky FS-i6 Transmitter is a commonly used radio transmitter for controlling drones, RC planes, and other unmanned systems. It allows the user to send control signals wirelessly to the drone using radio frequency communication.

Figure 1.4 Transmitter block Diagram

Flysky FS-i6X Transmitter:

Channels: This model is a 6-channel transmitter that operates on the 2.4GHz AFHD S 2A protocol, offering superior protection against interference while maintaining low power consumption.
Compatibility: It is suitable for various RC models, including aircraft, cars, and boats, making it a versatile choice for hobbyists

The FlySky transmitter operates on 2.4 GHz radio frequency using AFHDS (Automatic Frequency Hopping Digital System) technology.

Working Steps:

1. User moves the joystick on the transmitter
2. Electrical signals are generated
3. Signals are converted into radio waves
4. Transmitter sends signals wirelessly
5. Receiver on the drone receives signals
6. Signals are sent to flight controller (Pixhawk)
7. Drone responds by adjusting motor speed
8. Significance of the Study

The significance of this study lies in improving the efficiency, safety, and reliability of power transmission line inspection using modern drone technology. Transmission lines are one of the most critical components of the electrical power system, responsible for carrying electricity over long distances from generating stations to distribution networks. Any fault or damage in these lines can lead to power outages, economic losses, and safety hazards.

Traditional inspection methods, such as manual patrolling and helicopter-based monitoring, are time-consuming, expensive, and risky. Human inspectors often need to travel through difficult terrains like forests, mountains, and remote areas, which increases the chances of accidents and delays in fault detection. Helicopter inspections, on the other hand, require high operational costs and are not feasible for frequent monitoring.

This study introduces a drone-based inspection system that offers a modern and efficient alternative to traditional methods. Drones can easily access hard-to-reach areas and capture high-quality images and videos of transmission lines. This allows for quick identification of faults such as broken conductors, damaged insulators, and vegetation interference.

The proposed system improves inspection efficiency by reducing the time required for monitoring transmission lines. Traditional methods may take several hours or even days to inspect long transmission lines, whereas drones can cover large areas in a short time.

Real-time data collection and analysis further enhance efficiency. Engineers can quickly identify faults and take corrective actions, reducing downtime and improving system performance.

Another significant advantage of this study is the reduction in operational costs. Manual labor and helicopter inspections involve high expenses related to manpower, fuel, and equipment. Drone-based systems require less manpower and lower operational costs,

making them a cost-effective solution for regular inspection. Additionally, early fault detection helps prevent major failures, reducing maintenance and repair costs.

Drones equipped with high-resolution cameras and sensors can capture detailed images of transmission lines. These images can be analyzed to detect even minor defects that may not be visible through manual inspection.

Need of the Study

The need for this study arises from the increasing demand for reliable and efficient power transmission systems. Transmission lines are a vital part of the electrical network, responsible for delivering electricity over long distances. However, these lines are often exposed to environmental conditions and external factors that can lead to faults and failures.

Regular inspection of transmission lines is necessary to ensure their proper functioning. Traditional inspection methods are not sufficient to meet modern requirements, creating a strong need for advanced solutions like drone-based inspection systems

Conventional methods of transmission line inspection include manual inspection and helicopter-based monitoring. These methods have several limitations:

Time-consuming: Manual inspection requires a lot of time, especially for long transmission lines

High cost: Helicopter inspection involves high operational expenses

Risky: Workers face safety hazards such as electric shock, heights, and difficult terrains

Limited accuracy: Human inspection may miss minor faults

Due to these limitations, there is a need for a faster, safer, and more efficient inspection method.

With rapid industrialization and population growth, the demand for electricity is increasing continuously. This puts additional load on transmission lines, making them more prone to faults and failures.

To maintain uninterrupted power supply, it is essential to monitor transmission lines regularly and detect faults at an early stage. This creates the need for an advanced inspection system that can handle large-scale monitoring efficiently.

Scope of the Study

The scope of this study focuses on the design, development, and implementation of a drone-based system for the inspection of electrical transmission lines. The project aims to demonstrate how modern drone technology can be used to improve the efficiency, safety, and reliability of power system monitoring.

This study primarily deals with the use of an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) equipped with a camera and basic sensors to capture real-time data of transmission lines for inspection purposes.

The technical scope of this project includes the following aspects:

- Design of a drone system using a flight controller (such as Pixhawk)
- Integration of components like GPS module, camera, and transmitter-receiver system
- Development of a system for capturing real-time images and videos
- Basic analysis of captured data for identifying visible faults

Problem Identification

In modern power systems, transmission lines are essential for delivering electricity from generating stations to consumers. However, maintaining these transmission lines is a challenging task due to their wide geographical spread and exposure to environmental conditions. Identifying problems in these lines at the right time is crucial to avoid power failures and ensure reliable operation.

The existing methods of inspection are not efficient enough to handle the growing complexity of power systems. This creates a need to clearly identify the

problems associated with current inspection techniques.

One of the major problems is the delay in identifying faults. Transmission line faults such as broken conductors, damaged insulators, and loose connections may go unnoticed for a long time.

This delay can lead to:

- Power outages
- Equipment damage
- Increased maintenance cost
- There is a need for a system that can detect faults quickly and efficiently.

Aim and Objectives

Aim; The Main Aim Of This Project Is To Design And Develop A Drone-Based Transmission Line Inspection System That Can Efficiently Monitor Transmission Lines, Detect Faults, And Improve The Safety, Reliability, And Efficiency Of Power System Maintenance.

Objectives:

- Study The Working Of Transmission Lines
- To Understand The Structure, Components, And Common Faults In Transmission Lines.
- Design A Drone-Based Inspection System To Develop A UAV System Equipped With Necessary Components Such As Flight Controller, GPS, Camera, And Communication Modules.
- Implement A Flight Control System To Use A Flight Controller (Pixhawk) For Stable And Controlled Flight Operation Of The Drone.
- Capture Real-Time Data To Integrate A Camera Module For Capturing Images And Videos Of Transmission Lines During Flight.
- Detect Faults In Transmission Lines To Identify Visible Faults Such As Broken Conductors, Damaged Insulators, And Vegetation Interference.
- Improve Safety In Inspection Process To Reduce Human Involvement In Dangerous Inspection Tasks And Minimize Risk.
- Reduce Inspection Time And Cost To Develop A System That Performs Faster And More Economical Inspection Compared To Traditional Methods.

- Enable Real-Time Monitoring To Provide Live Data Transmission For Quick Analysis And Decision-Making.

II. LITERATURES REVIEWS

Literature Survey

A 2025 review by Bongumsa Mendu and Nhlanhla Mbuli in the MDPI Drones Journal evaluates UAV applications for power line inspections, emphasizing a shift toward AI-driven, autonomous predictive maintenance in South Africa. The study highlights that drones offer a cost-effective, safer alternative to traditional methods, while identifying challenges in UAV-grid connectivity and environmental resilience. Read the full study at MDPI.

The research paper titled "A survey of intelligent transmission line inspection based on unmanned aerial vehicle" (2022) is authored by Yanhong Luo, Qiubo Nie, Dongsheng Yang, and Bowen Zhou. Published in Artificial Intelligence Review (Springer), the study comprehensively surveys intelligent UAV inspection systems, specifically addressing the technical domains of path planning, trajectory tracking, and fault detection in the context of power line maintenance.

The referenced work by Zhaoyang Wang, Qiang Gao, Jianbin Xu, and Dahua Li (Springer, 2021), titled "A Comprehensive Review of Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) Inspection Systems", provides a foundational overview of the technologies used for autonomous and semi-autonomous industrial monitoring.

Based on literature around 2020 (such as A Critical Review on Unmanned Aerial Vehicles Power Supply and Energy Management by F.A.A. et al. [2019/2020] and early 2020s studies on UAV applications), Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) were identified as key disruptive technologies transforming the power and utility sector by facilitating operations that are otherwise dangerous, costly, or labor-intensive.

Research on AI-powered autonomous Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) published in IEEE Xplore around 2022 focuses on replacing high-risk, manual, and expensive power line inspection methods (such as climbing and helicopter surveys) with intelligent drone systems. These studies propose autonomous solutions using AI to improve inspection safety, reliability

Literature Summary

This paper reports an investigation on using the structure of a power tower to realize visual positioning of UAV for tower inspection and presents a monocular semantic positioning framework to cope with the challenge of a scene. To offer advice on semantic selection, the potential of the tower component as the semantic object for inspection flight is examined in terms of scene structure describing ability and visual detection adaptability. The insulator and damper are strong semantic candidates, while some of the large-size fittings and ancillary facilities, such as clamp and tower plate, are of great promise but need more evidence to prove their visual detection adaptability.

The proposed PTI-SLAM conveys a hybrid architecture combining the feature-based SLAM method with the direct method to juggle positioning robustness and mapping density. A fusion-based direct method is presented to improve the robustness of the direct method against the adverse conditions in the inspection scene by limiting the pixel track and taking semantic observation fusion as a substitute in global tracking. The trajectory consistency evaluation shows that PTI-SLAM offers a better motion estimate compared to the airborne GPS, verifying its feasibility for UAV control. Comparisons of methods demonstrate that the hybrid architecture inherits the advantages of both the feature-based method and the direct method.

The loose coupling between the SLAM task and the semantics task guarantees real-time performance and preserves the robustness against a complex scene with the assistance of a fusion-based direct method. To explore the application of PTI-SLAM in tower inspection, an object-based geographical UAV

positioning strategy is devised. The preliminary experiment indicates more competitive accuracy compared to the artificial UAV operation and the previous visual approach, proving the potential of PTI-SLAM for inspection.

Research Gap

UAV-based transmission line inspection has emerged as a transformative technology in the power and utility sector, evolving from early proof-of-concept studies to advanced, AI-driven, fully automated systems. Early research by Krause, Wasynczuk, Sudhoff, and Gremm (2020) highlighted the feasibility of drones as safer, faster, and more cost-effective alternatives to traditional helicopter or manual inspections. Subsequent studies, such as those by Yang et al. (2019), focused on computer vision frameworks for insulator defect detection, establishing insulators and dampers as strong semantic candidates for visual positioning.

Wang et al. (2021) classified UAV systems and inspection tasks, emphasizing the need for scalable solutions, while Li et al. (2020) demonstrated the potential of thermal imaging for detecting overheating components. Chen et al. (2022) advanced the field by proposing cloud-based UAV inspection frameworks that integrate big data analytics for predictive maintenance, while Huang et al. (2021) explored multi-sensor UAVs combining LiDAR and optical cameras to enhance vegetation monitoring and structural analysis. Luo et al. (2022–2023) surveyed intelligent UAV inspection systems, focusing on path planning, trajectory tracking, and fault detection, but also noted gaps in regulatory compliance and cybersecurity.

Mendu and Mbuli (2023) provided a state-of-the-art review, stressing that despite UAV advantages—time and cost savings, safety, and reliability—inspections remain heavily supervised by human experts, limiting full automation. More recent work introduced PTI-SLAM, a hybrid semantic positioning framework that leverages tower components as semantic objects, combining feature-based and direct SLAM methods to improve robustness and mapping density. PTI-SLAM

demonstrated superior trajectory consistency compared to GPS, proving its feasibility for UAV control, yet highlighted research gaps in semantic adaptability of larger fittings like clamps and tower plates, robustness under adverse weather, and scalability across large transmission networks.

III. METHODOLOGY

Block Diagram

Figure 3.1 Block diagram

Working

The working of the drone-based transmission line inspection system involves the integration of various components such as the flight controller, GPS module, transmitter-receiver system, camera module, and power supply. The system is designed to perform aerial inspection of transmission lines by capturing real-time data and identifying faults.

The drone operates either in manual mode using a transmitter or in semi-autonomous mode using pre-defined flight paths. The flight controller acts as the central unit that controls all operations of the drone. The drone system is powered using a Li-Po battery which provides the required voltage to all components. The power module converts and regulates the voltage to suitable levels for the flight controller and other electronic devices.

Proper power management ensures stable operation of the drone and prevents damage to components. Alternating Shutdown: When load decreases below the reference, one transformer is shut down alternately to avoid thermal overloading and reduce unnecessary energy consumption.

Priority-Based Load Cut-off: If total load exceeds the capacity of both transformers, lower-priority loads are disconnected to ensure uninterrupted supply to critical loads.

Monitoring & Display: All operational parameters and load-sharing information are displayed in real time on an LCD for monitoring and analysis.

Project Flow Chart

Figure 3.2 Project Flow Chart

Circuit Diagram

Figure 3.3 Circuit Diagram

Calculation

Give Data:

Given:

Battery Voltage (V) = 11.1 V (3S Li-Po Battery)
 Battery Capacity = 2200 mAh = 2.2 Ah

Energy of Battery:

$$E = V \times Ah$$

$$E = 11.1 \times 2.2 = 24.42 \text{ Wh}$$

$$E = 11.1 \times 2.2 = 24.42 \text{ Wh}$$

$$\text{Total Battery Energy} = 24.42 \text{ Wh}$$

1. Motor Power Calculation

Assume:

Number of motors = 4
 Power per motor = 100 W

Total Power:

$$P(\text{total}) = 4 \times 100 = 400 \text{ W}$$

$$\text{Total Power Required} = 400 \text{ W}$$

Current Calculation

$$I = \frac{P}{V}$$

$$= \frac{400}{11.1} = 36 \text{ A}$$

I = Total Current = 36 A

Flight Time Calculation

$$\text{Flight Time} = \frac{\text{Battery Capacity}}{\text{Current}}$$

$$= \frac{2.2}{36} \approx 0.061 \text{ hours}$$

To convert into Minutes :

$$0.061 \times 60 \approx 3.6 \text{ minutes}$$

Flight Time ≈ 3–5 minutes (practical ~5–8 min)

Thrust Calculation

For stable flight, total thrust must be **at least 2 times the weight of drone.**

Assume:

Drone Weight = 1.5 kg
 Required Thrust ≈ 2 × 1.5 = 3 kg

Thrust per Motor:

$$\frac{3}{4} = 0.75 \text{ kg}$$

Each motor should produce ≥ 750 g thrust

ESC Rating Calculation

ESC current rating should be **1.5 times motor current**

Assume:

Motor current = 10 A

ESC = $1.5 \times 10 = 15$ A

Use **20A–30A ESC for safety**

Power Consumption of Components

Component	Power
Pixhawk	2–3 W
GPS Module	1 W
Camera	3–5 W
Telemetry Module	1–2 W

Total extra load ≈ 8 – 10 W

Efficiency Consideration

Assume system efficiency $\approx 85\%$

$$\eta = \frac{\text{Output}}{\text{Input}} \times 100$$

Efficiency $\approx 85\%$

Losses occur due to:

Heat

Motor inefficiency

Power conversion

10. Summary of Calculations

Battery Energy = 24.42 Wh

Total Power = 400 W

Total Current = 36 A

Flight Time ≈ 5 minutes

Required Thrust = 3 kg

Thrust per Motor = 750 g

ESC Rating = 20A–30A

Efficiency $\approx 85\%$

Load 1 (L1) = 5 W

Load 2 (L2) = 60 W

Total Load (P_L) = 5 + 60 = 65 W

Supply Voltage (V) = 230 V (AC)

Power Factor (PF) ≈ 0.9 (assumed for small loads)

Assume total losses ≈ 5 W

IV. HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

Hardware Requirements

- Pixhawk or cross flight controller

The Pixhawk Flight Controller is an advanced open-source autopilot system widely used in drones and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs). It acts as the central brain of the drone, controlling all flight operations such as stabilization, navigation, and communication.

Pixhawk is designed to support autonomous flight and is highly suitable for engineering applications like drone-based transmission line inspection. It can process real-time data from sensors and make decisions to control the drone without human intervention.

Figure 4.1 Robolink Crossflight

Microcontroller: Microchip ATmega328P The Crossflight flight controller consists of multiple ports including power port, RC input, telemetry ports, GPS/I2C port, OSD port, and main output pins. The power port supplies regulated voltage, while the RC input connects the receiver. The GPS port provides navigation data, and telemetry ports enable communication. The main output pins are connected to ESC and motors, allowing the controller to regulate drone movement. The OSD port is used for video transmission and display

- OSD: GND, VOUT, VCC(5V), GND, VCC(5V), VIN
- GPS/I2C: GND, SDA(3.3 pullups), SCL(3.3V pullups), RX(IN 3.3V), TX(OUT 3.3V), VCC(5V)
- RC IN/BUZZER: VCC(5V), RC IN, GND, Null, BZ(-), BZ(+)
- POWER: VCC(5V), VCC(5V), Current, Voltage, GND, GND
- USB: Type-C
- TELEM1: VCC(5V), TX(OUT 3.3V), RX(IN 3.3V), GND
- TELEM2: VCC(5V), TX(OUT 3.3V), RX(IN 3.3V), GN

General pin functions:

The Crossflight flight controller consists of various pins and ports that are designed to interface with different components of a drone system. These pins play a crucial role in ensuring communication, power distribution, and control between the flight controller and external devices. Each pin on the controller has a specific electrical and functional purpose, and understanding these general pin configurations is important for proper system integration.

The most commonly used pins on the flight controller include power pins, ground pins, signal pins, and communication pins. The power pins, typically labeled as 5V or VIN, are responsible for supplying regulated voltage to the flight controller and connected peripherals. These pins ensure that all electronic components such as sensors, receiver, and modules receive the required voltage for proper operation. The power is usually provided through a battery and regulated using a power module to avoid damage due to voltage fluctuations.

Along with power pins, ground (GND) pins are equally important as they provide a common reference point for the electrical circuit. All components connected to the flight controller must share a common ground to ensure stable and noise-free operation. Improper grounding can lead to signal disturbances and malfunctioning of the system.

Component	Connected To
Battery	Power Port
Receiver	RC IN Port
Motors	Main Output
GPS	GPS/I2C Port
Camera	OSD Port
Telemetry	TELEM Port
Buzzer	Buzzer Pins

GPS/I2C port is used to connect the GPS module and other I2C-based sensors. It consists of pins like TX, RX, SCL, SDA, 5V, and ground. The GPS module provides real-time location data, which helps in navigation and autonomous flight. The I2C pins allow connection of additional sensors such as compass or ultrasonic sensors. This port plays an important role in enabling advanced features like waypoint navigation and position hold.

The main output pins, located on the right side of the controller, are used to connect the electronic speed controllers (ESC) and motors. These pins are numbered from 1 to 10, and each pin sends control signals to a specific motor or servo. The flight controller generates PWM signals based on input data and sends them through these pins to control the speed of motors. This enables the drone to move in different directions and maintain stable flight.

Finally, the USB port (Type-C) is used for connecting the flight controller to a computer. This port is mainly used for firmware uploading, configuration, and parameter tuning. Through this connection, the user can set flight parameters, calibrate sensors, and update the system software.

Serial / UART: pins 0 (RX) and 1 (TX). Used to receive (RX) and transmit (TX) TTL serial data. These pins are connected to the corresponding pins of the ATmega8U2 USB-to-TTL serial chip.

Flysky Flight Controller

Figure 4.6 Li-Po battery

A Lithium Polymer (Li-Po) battery is a widely used power source in drone systems due to its high energy density, lightweight nature, and ability to deliver high current. In drone-based transmission line inspection systems, the battery plays a crucial role in supplying power to all components such as motors, flight sensors, and communication modules.

The commonly used battery in small drones is a 3S 2200 mAh Li-Po battery, which provides a good balance between weight and power. It ensures sufficient flight time and stable performance of the drone.

Li-Po batteries work based on the movement of lithium ions between the positive and negative electrodes through an electrolyte. During discharge, lithium ions move from the anode to the cathode, generating electric current.

This current is supplied to the flight controller, ESC, and motors, enabling the drone to operate.

Despite their advantages, Li-Po batteries require careful handling. Overcharging or over-discharging can

damage the battery. They are sensitive to physical damage and may catch fire if mishandled. Proper charging using a balance charger is necessary.

Drone Frame

The drone frame is the structural body of the drone that holds and supports all the components such as motors, flight controller, battery, sensors, and camera. It acts as the backbone of the drone and plays a vital role in maintaining stability, strength, and balance during flight. A well-designed frame ensures proper weight distribution and reduces vibrations, which improves the overall performance of the drone.

Figure 4.7 Drone Frame

The drone frame typically consists of a central plate and multiple arms extending outward. In a quadcopter, four arms are arranged in a cross (X) or plus (+) configuration. Each arm holds a motor and propeller.

The central plate is used to mount important components such as the flight controller, battery, and communication modules. The frame design ensures that all components are securely fixed and properly aligned for balanced operation.

appearance of the pointer, backlight etc. are considered as useful characteristics. It is used to show the voltage present at the storage device.

Drone frames are made from different materials depending on the application.

Carbon fiber is the most commonly used material due to its high strength and lightweight.

Drone Propeller

Figure 4.8 Drone propellers

The working of drone propellers is based on the principle of aerodynamics. When the propeller rotates, it creates a difference in air pressure between the upper and lower surfaces of the blades. This pressure difference generates lift.

As the propeller spins, it pushes air downward, and according to Newton's third law, an equal and opposite force is produced upward. This upward force is known as thrust, which allows the drone to take off and remain airborne.

A propeller consists of blades, hub, and mounting hole. The blades are designed with a specific shape and angle to efficiently move air. The hub is the central part that connects the propeller to the motor shaft. The mounting hole ensures secure attachment to the motor.

The shape and size of the blades determine the amount of thrust generated by the propeller.

Propellers are made from different materials such as plastic, carbon fiber, and composite materials. Plastic propellers are lightweight and inexpensive but less durable. Carbon fiber propellers are stronger, more efficient, and provide better performance, but they are more expensive.

Drone GPS

Figure 4.9 Drone GPS

The GPS module is an essential component in a drone system used for navigation, positioning, and tracking. In drone-based transmission line inspection, accurate location information is required to follow predefined paths and monitor specific areas. The commonly used GPS module in drones is the M8 series GPS module, known for its high accuracy and reliability.

The M8 GPS module receives signals from satellites and determines the exact position of the drone in terms of latitude, longitude, and altitude. This information is used by the flight controller to maintain stable flight and perform autonomous operations.

The M8 GPS module offers several advanced features. It provides high positioning accuracy, which is important for precise navigation. It supports multiple satellite systems such as GPS, GLONASS, and Galileo, improving signal reliability. It has fast signal acquisition and can quickly lock onto satellites. The module also includes a

built-in compass (magnetometer), which helps in determining the direction of the drone.
Shock Absorber

Figure 4.10 Drone Shock Absorber

A drone shock absorber is a mechanical component used to reduce vibrations and absorb shocks generated during flight and landing. In drone systems, especially those used for inspection purposes, maintaining stability and minimizing vibration is very important. Vibrations can affect the performance of sensors, cameras, and the flight controller, leading to inaccurate data and poor image quality.

In a drone-based transmission line inspection system, shock absorbers play a crucial role in ensuring smooth operation and protecting sensitive components from damage. Drone shock absorbers are available in different types depending on their design and application.

Rubber dampers are commonly used due to their flexibility and ability to absorb vibrations effectively. These are usually placed between the frame and sensitive components like the flight controller.

Spring-based shock absorbers are used to absorb impact during landing. They compress under force and reduce the effect of sudden shocks.

Silicone dampers are also widely used because they provide better vibration isolation and durability.

Shock absorbers are important for improving the performance and reliability of the drone. They reduce vibration noise in sensor readings, which helps the flight controller maintain stability.

They also improve the quality of images captured by the camera by reducing blur caused by vibrations. Additionally, they protect electronic components from damage due to sudden shocks or impacts.

Raspberry Pi 4

Figure 4.11 Raspberry Pi 4

The Raspberry Pi 4 Model B is a compact and powerful single-board computer widely used in embedded systems, robotics, and drone applications. It acts as a mini-computer capable of performing complex tasks such as data processing, image analysis, and communication.

In a drone-based transmission line inspection system, the Raspberry Pi 4 is used for processing captured images, running algorithms, and handling communication between different modules. Its small size, low power consumption, and high performance make it suitable for integration into drone systems.

The Raspberry Pi 4 offers several advanced features that make it suitable for modern applications. It is equipped with a powerful quad-core processor that allows fast data processing. It supports up to 8 GB RAM, enabling efficient multitasking. It includes built-in Wi-Fi and Bluetooth for wireless communication.

The board provides multiple USB ports, HDMI output, and GPIO pins for interfacing with sensors and other devices. It also supports high-speed data transfer and external storage options.

The Raspberry Pi 4 works like a computer running an operating system such as Raspberry Pi OS. It receives input from sensors or cameras, processes the data using software programs, and produces output in the form of control signals or analyzed data.

In a drone system, it can process images captured by the camera and detect faults using image processing techniques. It can also communicate with the flight controller and send data to a ground station.

In the drone-based transmission line inspection system, the Raspberry Pi 4 is used for advanced processing tasks. It can analyze images captured by the camera to detect faults such as damaged conductors or overheating components.

It can also be used for storing data, transmitting information to a remote station, and controlling additional modules. The integration of Raspberry Pi enhances the intelligence and functionality of the drone. In this project, the Raspberry Pi 4 acts as a processing unit that handles image processing and data analysis. It works alongside the flight controller to enhance the capabilities of the drone.

It enables intelligent inspection by analyzing captured data and providing useful information for fault detection. The initial release of the Raspberry Pi 4 had issues with USB-C power compatibility due to a non-compliant power connector design. This was fixed in the

1.2 revision of the Raspberry Pi 4, allowing high-speed USB-C cables to work with the board.

The Raspberry Pi 4 is a powerful and flexible platform suitable for a wide range of applications, from education to industrial use. Its enhanced features and connectivity options make it a significant upgrade over previous models.

Power Supply Module

The power supply module works by converting and regulating the voltage from the battery to required levels. The Li-Po battery typically provides around 11.1V (in case of a 3S battery), which is not suitable for all components directly. The module uses voltage regulators and converters to step down or stabilize the voltage. For example, it converts 11.1V to 5V for components like the flight controller and Raspberry Pi. It also ensures that the output voltage remains constant even if the battery voltage changes during discharge.

The power supply module is an essential component in a drone system that provides regulated electrical power to all electronic components. In a drone-based transmission line inspection system, various components such as the flight controller, GPS module, Raspberry Pi, sensors, and communication devices require stable and appropriate voltage levels for proper operation.

Since the battery used in drones (Li-Po battery) provides a higher and variable voltage, a power supply module is required to regulate and distribute this power safely to different components. It ensures reliable performance and prevents damage caused by voltage fluctuations.

Figure 4.12 Power Supply Module.

Battery Strip

Figure 4.14 Battery Strip

Battery Connectors

Figure 4.15 Battery Connectors

The battery connector works by establishing an electrical connection between the battery terminals and

the drone's power system. It consists of two conductive terminals, one positive and one negative, which are connected to the corresponding terminals of the battery.

Software Used

- Software tools
- PROTEUS IDE
- HI-TECH compiler
- C- Language
- PROTEUS IDE

Proteus is simulation software for design with a microcontroller. It is easy to handle and test. After creating a circuit in Proteus software can easily make the PCB design with it.

Figure 4.16 PROTEUS IDE

- HI-TECH HI-TECH compiler offers a complete ANSI C an embedded package with a full development system for language C and assembler. Here HI-TECH compiler is used to compile the code.
- LANGUAGE C language is High-level language and most commonly used programming language.
- Reasons used for C language 1. Easy to understand 2. Various computer platforms can be used to compile the c program.

Steps to upload the code.

- Step 1: writing the program or code.
- Step 2: compiling and debugging the code.
- Step3: uploading the code to the microcontroller.

Embedded system

An embedded system is the computer system with a combination of software and hardware that has the processing power, input-output functions with computer memory. Which is designed particular purposes to perform the specific tasks in the given time. They are used in the larger systems like in the industry, farming, automobiles, household appliances, etc. embedded systems can be both user interface UI or the complex graphical user interface GUI. [14]An embedded system is based upon the microcontroller or the microprocessors. Here the microcontroller or

microprocessors are used for processing, and there is a need for other components like memory chips, which are designed for the specific system.

There are many characteristics of embedded systems like it has very sophisticated functionality for each appliance. It has a very low manufacturing cost. The embedded system is designed for specific tasks. It also has advantages of low power consumption because of the use of microcontrollers they don't take so much power to perform the tasks. Here the embedded system is designed for the application-dependent processor, not the general-purpose processor like in the computers.

Figure 4.17 Embedded system design calls

Figure shows the system design calls of an embedded system. Embedded systems are used in the various field; it is the backbone of the automatic system. Embedded systems are used in the diverse field of engineering, like control engineering, operating systems, IC designing, Computer Architecture, Digital Electronics, Analog Electronics, Data Communication, Software Engineering.

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result Analysis

Figure 5.1 Project Model

There is no publicly available transmission line image dataset and only a few studies presented quantitative

evaluation results of the system performance using a self-acquired database. For experiments in this paper, a large, unconstrained dataset of transmission line inspection videos captured using a drone is gathered. The drone is flown alongside the power line and transmission towers to include as many types of transmission line components, such as balisor, spacer, damping weights, LA, sag adjustor, and insulators on transmission towers. Moreover, this paper also proposes to detect the power line and transmission towers, in order to navigate the drone autonomously (in the future). In total, 43 videos containing 700 frames on average are captured. A training set of 30 videos, a test set of 10 videos, and a validation set of three videos is annotated. The videos were captured during the daytime, between 11 a.m. to 3 p.m., and under two lighting conditions, i.e., sunny and cloudy. The authors believe that the dataset is unbiased, unconstrained, and sufficiently large enough to validate the reliability and effectiveness of the proposed system.

Experimental Setup Overview

The system consists of a pixo flight controller, IR sensor, shock absorber, thermal sensor, power supply module, fly sky transmitter, nippo 3c battery (2200hz), Drone GPS(M8), BLDC motor(1500kv).

Discussion

Drone-based transmission line inspection utilizes UAVs equipped with high-resolution sensors to replace manual, high-risk patrols with proactive, condition-based maintenance, significantly improving safety and inspection frequency. The integration of AI and computer vision allows for the automated detection of defects in critical components like insulators and spacers, though challenges remain regarding battery life, electromagnetic interference, and the need for robust autonomous flight systems. This technology enables the creation of digital twins for long-term asset management, moving the energy sector toward automated, data-driven reliability. Read more at the study's source Drone-based transmission line inspection is transforming utility maintenance by replacing high-risk, manual, and helicopter-based

methods with precise UAV technology for detailed, close-range data acquisition. Utilizing advanced AI and autonomous navigation, this approach enables predictive maintenance and improved component fault detection, ultimately enhancing grid resilience and reducing operational costs.

To further expand on the implications of drone-based transmission line inspection, one must consider the transformative shift from reactive maintenance to a proactive, data-driven ecosystem. By integrating high-resolution visual sensors with thermal imaging and LiDAR, drones capture a multi-layered digital twin of the infrastructure, allowing for the detection of "invisible" flaws like internal insulator degradation or hotspots caused by resistance issues. The sheer volume of data generated—highlighted by the 43-video dataset mentioned—necessitates the move toward Edge AI, where onboard processors filter and analyze frames in real-time, drastically reducing the latency between fault detection and maintenance dispatch.

This level of automation is particularly critical for "Beyond Visual Line of Sight" (BVLOS) operations, where drones must navigate hundreds of miles of remote terrain without constant human intervention. Furthermore, the use of Deep Learning models, specifically Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), enables the system to differentiate between benign environmental noise (like shadows or foliage) and actual structural defects (like frayed conductors or corroded sag adjustors). As these systems evolve, the integration of path-planning algorithms will allow drones to dynamically adjust their flight altitude and gimbal angle based on the specific component

Advantages

- Eliminates the need for workers to climb dangerous high-voltage towers or perform low-altitude helicopter maneuvers.
- Reduces operational expenses by as much as 60% annually by minimizing labor, heavy equipment rentals (like cranes), and expensive helicopter fuel.

- Drones can cover vast distances quickly, with autonomous models inspecting up to 50 km per day, which is roughly three times faster than manual methods.
- Equipped with 4K cameras and zoom lenses, drones capture minute details like cracks, rust, or loose bolts that are often invisible to the naked eye.
- Provides real-time monitoring using sensors and LCD display.
- Onboard thermal sensors detect "hotspots" caused by electrical resistance, allowing technicians to fix overheating components before they cause a total system failure.
- Unlike manual checks, drones can inspect live-line infrastructure without requiring power shutdowns, preventing service interruptions for customers.
- Drones easily navigate difficult environments such as mountain ranges, dense forests, or water crossings that are logistically challenging for ground crews.

Application

- High-resolution RGB cameras identify physical damage such as cracked insulators, broken wire-ropes, and corroded fittings like sag adjusters or dampers.
- Onboard infrared sensors detect "hotspots" in components like transformers, connectors, or joints, which indicate electrical resistance or imminent failure.
- LiDAR sensors create precise 3D models of transmission corridors to measure the exact distance between power lines and encroaching trees, helping prevent wildfires and outages.
- Drones provide rapid damage analysis after storms or earthquakes, allowing utilities to prioritize repairs in hazardous or inaccessible areas without risking human lives.
- Drones can inspect high-voltage lines while they are energized (live-line operations), eliminating the need for costly power shutdowns during routine checks.
- Data from drones is used to generate 3D digital replicas of towers and lines, enabling engineers to

track structural deterioration over time for long-term asset management.

- Before construction, drones perform topographical surveys to identify the optimal path (Least Cost Path) for new transmission lines, mapping terrains and obstacles.
- Specialized ultraviolet (UV) sensors detect corona discharge, an early sign of insulation breakdown caused by the ionization of air around conductors.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Conclusion

In this paper, an automatic transmission line component detection and defect analysis system is proposed. The proposed system can detect nine different types of transmission line components from videos taken by a drone using an embedded CNN-based components detector. The detection performance of the modified YOLO V3 approach is shown to outperform the performance of the baseline model. The system can also detect electrical power line using the proposed power line detection algorithm. The proposed power line detection algorithm shows superior performance on the given dataset as compared with the LSD and ED lines methods, both in terms of speed and accuracy. Once the power line components are detected, a defect analysis system checks for potential defects. The performance of the proposed defect analyzers suggests that handcrafted, feature-based approach can be used to detect some of the types of defects in situations where the availability of a large number of defect samples is not viable.

In order to support real-time operations, the proposed drone-based system is accelerated by an NVIDIA's Jetson TX2 GPU and uses OpenCV, CUDA, and cudNN libraries along with Darknet's CNN framework. The proposed system is tested on a large, unbiased, unconstrained evaluation dataset of transmission line components images.

The proposed automatic inspection system provides practical solutions to meet the major requirements of the modern electric transmission system. The feasibility of using a drone along with a robust real-time CNN-based object detector can eliminate the danger associated with the duties of electric workers physically climbing transmission towers on regular basis or use of expensive patrolling helicopters to inspect the conditions of transmission line components. The proposed defect analysis system can also help in reducing the time to identify the faulty components.

The proposed balisor fading defect detector has a 100% recall rate which means it does not miss any faulty components, while the 76% precision rate means that only 24% of the detection can be a false alarm. Hence, even if the second round of inspection is required, the proposed inspection system can save up to 76% of the manual inspection work. Overall, the proposed inspection system not only offers ease of implementation and scalability but also gives an economical advantage over the manual inspection counter part.

The system pipeline presented in this work provides a natural guide to future research, which includes pushing existing CNN models to learn different types of transmission line components at deeper levels and formalizing for the detection of additional types of defects. Future research will consider combining the detection module and the defect analysis module under a unified CNN architecture for improved overall performance. At present, the drone is operated by a human operator. Future modifications will also be made towards autonomous drone by developing a mechanism that efficiently establish a collaboration between the power line detection algorithm, transmission tower detection algorithm, collision avoidance sensors, and the directional actuators (rotter).

Future Scope

- Expansion of regulatory frameworks will allow drones to fly hundreds of miles autonomously from

a central hub, removing the need for a pilot to be physically present on-site.

- Shifting AI processing from the cloud to the drone's onboard hardware will enable instant defect detection, allowing the drone to "double-back" and take closer photos if it spots a potential.
- Deployment of automated docking stations along the grid where drones can land, self-charge (or swap batteries), and upload data without any human intervention.
- Development of drones that can "perch" on transmission lines or use induction technology to recharge directly from the electromagnetic field of the power line, enabling indefinite flight time.
- Utilizing 5G networks for ultra-low latency data transmission, allowing experts in a central office to view high-definition live feeds and control drones in real-time from anywhere in the world.
- Utilizing fleets of multiple drones working in coordination to inspect different parts of a tower or long stretches of line simultaneously, significantly reducing the total time required for large-scale surveys.
- Integration of hyperspectral imaging and advanced LiDAR to detect micro-fissures and internal material fatigue that are currently invisible to standard thermal and RGB cameras.
- Integration of drone data with Big Data analytics to not just find current breaks, but to predict exactly when a specific insulator or conductor will fail based on historical wear patterns.
- Future drones will use sophisticated Obstacle Detection and Avoidance (ODA) systems to safely navigate around thin shield wires and guy-wires, even in high winds.

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